

The Philosophers' Stone: History, Myth, Chemistry and Modern Medical Applications

By S.E.S. Medina, MD

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The Ouroboros and the Squared Circle

The metaphysical property of infinity is represented by the Ouroboros, an ancient pictogram of a serpent or dragon swallowing its own tail. Alchemical texts from the Middle-Ages often used the image in their writings. Within the Ouroboros is contained the Squared Circle, an alchemical symbol delineating the synergy of the four elements of matter resulting in the creation of the Philosophers' Stone. (Original Artwork by S.E.S. MD)

“Of all Elixirs, Gold is supreme and the most important for us... gold can keep the body indestructible... Drinkable gold will cure all illnesses, it renews and restores.”

Paracelsus (1493-1541 AD) – *Coelum Philosophorum* ⁽¹⁾

“The universal medicine which cures all human and metallic diseases is concealed in gold and its magnet (antimony)”

Johannes de Monte Snyder (1625-1670 AD) *Commentaire Sur la Médecine Universalle (Alchimie)* ⁽¹⁾

History and Myth Surrounding the Legend of the Philosophers' Stone

Gold preparations employed as therapeutics have existed for thousands of years in Western and Eastern cultures. ⁽²⁾

The Chinese were the first to prepare and use colloidal gold as the alchemical drug of longevity. ⁽²⁾

The word “alchemy” takes its origin from the Chinese words: Kim (gold) and Yeh (juice). Subsequently, the Arabs took the word “kimyeh” (gold juice), and by adding the definitive article, “al,” generated the word “al-kimiya,” which then evolved into alchemy. ⁽²⁾

The mysteries of the Philosophers' Stone have tantalized scholars and fortune seekers throughout history with its promise of immortality and wealth. ⁽¹⁾

However, the “Philosophers' Stone,” was actually two interrelated substances:

- Universal Medicine – unnatural longevity conferred to anyone who drank it (*Aurum Potabile*—gold that is safe to drink).
- Powder of Projection – a substance used to transmute base metals such as lead, mercury, or copper, into alchemical gold.

The earliest written account in Western culture describing the Stone is ascribed to Zosimos of Panopolis, an Egyptian-born Greek alchemist (c. 300 AD) in his *Cheirkometa*. ⁽³⁾

It was Zosimos' contention that the women of Earth were taught metallurgy, which included fabrication of the Stone, when they were taken as wives by the fallen angels of heaven. ⁽³⁾

An earlier origin of this forbidden knowledge is described in the anonymously authored medieval text, the *Gloria Mundi* (1620):

“Let me then tell you, who would be a true lover of this Art that it was first delivered by God to Adam in Paradise.” ⁽⁴⁾

As described in Genesis 3:22-24, the expulsion of Adam and Eve from the Garden of Eden by God resulted in humans losing the opportunity to eat from the Tree of Life and thus forfeiting the Divine Gift of Immortality. Logically, Adam would be fiercely interested in regaining some of that longevity.

It is speculated Adam passed knowledge of the Philosophers' Stone to the biblical patriarchs (such as Methuselah) which could explain their unnaturally long life spans described in the Hebrew Old Testament. ⁽¹⁾

St. Augustine of Hippo, fifth century Roman philosopher and Christian theologian, spoke about the revocation of the immortality of Adam and Eve upon expulsion from the Garden of Eden:

“—their bodies were not indeed growing old and senile, so as to be brought in the end to an inevitable death. This condition was granted them by the wonderful Grace of God and was derived from the Tree of Life which was in Paradise.”⁽¹⁾

Biblical accounts were taken as literal historical events by alchemists. Reading about the long-lived biblical patriarchs convinced them they could lengthen the human lifespan.

Alchemists concluded the patriarchs must have possessed a lost technology permitting prolonged longevity. Therefore, discovering the arcane secret of the Philosophers' Stone could permit life-prolongation.

The earliest Western accounts detailing the materials, methods and applications of the Stone are conveyed in the writings of the Alexandrian alchemist and scholar, Maria Hebraea, in the second century AD. ⁽¹⁾

The two methods she used to make the Stone became known as the *Ars Magna* (Great Art) and the *Ars Brevis* (Brief Art).

Maria Hebraea asserted the Philosophers' Stone was a legacy of the race of Abraham.

At the time of Maria's work in Alexandria, the art of alchemy was called *chrysopoeia* - meaning gold making. The procedure of aurification involved converting copper to a unique type of alchemical gold.

The Alexandrian school of alchemy headed by Maria noted that sulfide ores, such as cinnabar (HgS) and stibnite (Sb₂S₃) occurred alongside deposits of gold. This made the early alchemists conclude metal ores and base metals underwent an organic geological maturation process ending in the valuable yellow metal. ⁽¹⁾

It is interesting to note Alexandrian alchemists did not study the therapeutic effects of ingestible gold preparations. In contrast, European and Islamic alchemists pursued the Stone as a rejuvenating and medicinal substance. ⁽¹⁾

The Philosophers' Stone appeared within Western alchemical circles around the 12th century, but by the time of the 16th century Italian Renaissance, the legend of the Stone and its power was so extraordinary it rivaled the search for the Holy Grail or the Ark of the Covenant.

However, across the centuries, the knowledge regarding the Philosophers' Stone's genuine nature and uses became corrupted, leading to a major misunderstanding toward its actual "purpose."

It became understood the Stone's function was to transform base metals into genuine gold.

Instead, alchemical gold was a process where antimony and copper were "fermented" with the Elixir (Philosophers' Stone) and thus transmuted (changed) into a prized gold-antimonial bronze known as alchemical gold. ⁽¹⁾

George Starkey (1628-1665), a Colonial American physician and alchemist, wrote:

Some alchemists who are in search of our Arcanum seek to prepare something of a solid nature, because they have heard the object of their search described as a Stone.

Know, then, that it is called a stone, not because it is like a stone, but only because, by virtue of its fixed nature, it resists the action of fire as successfully as any stone. In species it is gold, more pure than the purest; it is fixed and incombustible like a stone, but its appearance is that of a very fine powder.

It does not exist in Nature, but has to be prepared by Art, in obedience to Nature's law. Its substance is in metals; but in form it differs widely from them, and in this sense the metals are not our Stone.

Thus, you see that though our Stone is made of gold alone, yet it is not common gold. ⁽¹⁾

The dual value of the Stone and the purpose of alchemy are best described by the 13th century philosopher, Franciscan friar and early European promoter of the scientific method, Roger Bacon:

Alchemy is the science which teaches how to make and generate a certain medicine, called elixir, which when projected onto metals or imperfect bodies perfects them completely at the moment of projection. ⁽¹⁾

The second power obtained from the Stone was to extend human life to its fullest potential. Bacon wrote:

That medicine which will remove all impurities and incorruptibilities from the lesser metals will also, in the opinion of the wise, take off so much of the incorruptibility of the body that human life may be prolonged for many centuries. ⁽¹⁾

Paracelsus (1493-1541) born Theophrastus von Hohenheim, was a lay theologian, physician, philosopher, and alchemist during the German Renaissance who focused on medicinal uses of alchemical products rather than alchemical gold manufacturing.

He wrote excitedly of the psycho-spiritual awakening and physical longevity resulting from ingestion of the Philosophers' Stone elixir. Paracelsus predicated a long life was achievable through a healthy diet, physical exercise and specifically from medicinals derived from the Stone. ⁽¹⁾

Paracelsus called the Stone the "Tincture of the Philosophers" and claimed synthesizing it by mixing fused and powdered gold-antimony glass with Butter of Antimony (antimony trichloride, SbCl_3).

He postulated the tincture was the secret "elixir of life" spoken of and used by the ancient Egyptians. Paracelsus claimed the Tincture was the "Universal Medicine" - a crucial element to achieving perfect health and well-being. ⁽¹⁾

Alchemists believed the Philosophers' Stone was not naturally occurring, but a complex substance created through skilled workmanship. The crucial first step was to purify the materials and blend them in the exact proportions.

The concoction was then sealed in a vessel and heated following an arduous temperature regimen. Finally, the Philosophers' Stone would generate itself through an auto-synthesizing transformation.

The physical characteristics of the Stone have been described as a heavy vermilion powder, a ruby-colored waxy substance, a deep-red, translucent crystal and even a golden-colored liquid.

Its odor has been reported similar to sea salt or by others as having no scent.

These unique descriptions sound conflicting, but in reality, are describing a product at distinct stages of purification. ⁽¹⁾

The three most common components necessary for confecting the Stone include:

- 1) **Gold** – the prime ingredient. The gold is first refined to an extremely high degree, and then reduced to colloidal gold, the finest particle size possible.
- 2) **Antimony** – this metalloid element exists in nature as a sulfide ore (stibnite - Sb_2S_3). After purification, antimony was called *regulus* in medieval times, or in earlier writings as *flowers of antimony*. Both purified antimony and stibnite were used at specific steps in the archetypal synthesis.
- 3) **Flux/Menstruum** – this final component possessed the ability of dissolving gold without chemical corrosion, yet retained the capacity to congeal, coagulate, or crystallize, under ideal conditions. The menstruum is described as metallic, yet translucent and viscous.

Alchemists guarded the secret for creating the Stone by occulting the true nature of the flux, also called the universal solvent in their writings by employing arcane symbolic names for it. ⁽¹⁾

Despite the use of colloidal gold by various clinicians in the 19th and 20th centuries for medicinal purposes, the Philosophers' Stone in its alchemical "aurum potable" has never been the subject of modern medical research to determine its potential therapeutic significance.

Until alchemical *aurum potable* is properly synthesized and studied in vivo through double-blind, placebo-controlled, randomized medical trials, and the study results peer-reviewed, its true potential will remain an enigma.

The Griffin

For alchemists, the mythical Greek chimera of eagle and lion, known as the Griffin, symbolized the completed Philosophers' Stone. The imaginary creature personified the unification of "fixed" gold and "volatile" antimony. ⁽¹⁾ (Original Artwork – S.E.S. Medina, MD)

Chemistry of the Philosophers' Stone

As stated earlier, the Philosophers' Stone is not a "stone" or "rock" in any physical sense. ⁽¹⁾

Aurum potable ("gold which is safe to drink") is a non-toxic colloidal or nano-particle gold with diameters of 15nm–300nm shown to enter and concentrate in a variety of organs and tissues. These include brain, testicles, immune cells, and the uterus (particularly the endometrium). ⁽⁵⁾ Semen has the highest gold concentrations of all biological tissues or fluids. ⁽⁶⁾

Elemental gold is one of the most chemically non-reactive metals known in living systems. Ingestion of particulate gold will not cause human illness because of its intrinsic inertness. ⁽⁷⁾

For thousands of years, traditional Indian-Hindu medicine has claimed preparations containing gold ⁽⁸⁾ ⁽⁹⁾ ⁽¹⁰⁾ have antioxidant and rejuvenating properties promoting longevity and decelerating aging. ⁽¹⁰⁾ ⁽¹¹⁾

One ancient therapeutic form of Indian nano-particle gold is known as *Swarna Bhasma* ("incinerated gold"). ⁽¹²⁾

The ancient Ayurvedic recipe, ⁽¹²⁾ involved three steps:

- **Shodhan** (purification of gold removing impurities)
- **Bhavna** (grinding with water to reduce particle size)
- **Maran** (high temperature incineration which causes further reduction in caliber)

The Bhavna and Maran treatments are repeated multiple times. A resulting reddish-brown powder is further ground until extremely fine, yielding *Swarna Bhasma*.

The particles obtained are 50-60 nm in diameter, a dimension that permits gastrointestinal absorption allowing the gold to reach tissues through the bloodstream. ⁽¹³⁾

However, in this discussion the procedures for preparation of the Philosophers' Stone reviewed will be those used in the Middle East and the West, which incorporate ancient chemical and metallurgical techniques.

The three primary ingredients required to manufacture the Philosophers' Stone are:

- 1) Purified gold (chemical symbol: Au)

By James St. John - Gold nugget (Australia) 4, CC BY 2.0,
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2) Antimony (chemical symbol: Sb) – this metalloid element possesses special physical properties which made it an extremely useful substance to alchemists.

Antimony

<http://images-of-elements.com/>, CC BY 3.0,
<https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=9084452>

Elemental antimony possesses many unique physical and chemical characteristics. It expands when liquefied and allowed to cool and solidify, exactly like water when it freezes to ice. Like gold, antimony does not tarnish or corrode.

Purified elemental antimony obtained from its sulfide (Sb_2S_3), is called the **Stone of the First Degree or Stone of the First Order**:⁽¹⁾

When antimony is melted (1,167 °F/ 616.3 °C), gold alloys with it (melting point of gold = 1,948 °F / 1050.2 °C) at a much lower temperature than normally required to smelt gold.

Upon cooling, the gold-antimony alloy becomes very brittle permitting easy grinding into an exceptionally fine powder.

Regarding the toxicity of elemental antimony and its compounds, they do not produce acute human health effects.

High oral intake in humans (>0.532 mgs/kg/day antimony) can cause adverse reactions such as diarrhea, joint and/or muscle pain, vomiting, pancreatitis, anemia, and an altered electrocardiogram.⁽¹⁴⁾⁽¹⁵⁾

The principal uses of antimony in the 21st century are as a flame retardant (60%), in alloys for batteries, metal bearings, solders, semiconductors, and in antiparasitic drugs administered to humans and animals.⁽¹⁵⁾

The primary forms of antimony employed by alchemists were:

- **Flowers of Antimony** – Antimony trioxide/sulfide ($\text{Sb}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{Sb}_2\text{S}_3$)
- **Glass of Antimony** – Antimony oxysulfate ($\text{Sb}_2\text{O}_2\text{SO}_4$)
- **Butter of Antimony** – Antimony trichloride (SbCl_3)
- **Powder of Algarotti** – Antimony oxychlorides (SbOCl ; $\text{Sb}_4\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_2$)

3) Flux/Menstruum - a substance which facilitates the dissolution of the gold/antimony mixture and permits its “fermentation” and later conversion to the Stone.

One common “flux” used in alchemy was *Butter of Antimony*, chemically known as antimony trichloride (SbCl_3), a soft solid at room temperature which when exposed to a moderate heat becomes molten and crystallizes when cooled.

If *Butter of Antimony* is heated to 73.4°C or higher, it melts into a thick, translucent liquid.

In European alchemical circles, *Butter of Antimony* was the preferred menstruum.⁽¹⁾

Another useful flux is Sal Ammoniac (NH_4Cl) which upon heating becomes a fiery vapor, decomposing into liquid and vaporous hydrogen chloride (HCl).

Sal Ammoniac assists by catalyzing the chemical reactions and physical changes that lead to creation of the Stone.⁽¹⁾

Stone of the Second Degree or Stone of the Second Order:⁽¹⁾ also known as the *Rebis* (*Lion's Blood*), meaning a “dual” substance, where a union of opposites into a single material is greater than the sum of the two parts.

Possession of the secret knowledge for the “correct proportion of components” was vital to producing proper Rebis.

It was customarily prepared via a two-step process:

- The first step - vitrification (to make a glass) - is performed by mixing purified elemental antimony with refined gold calx in just the precise percentages and then heated to yield a brittle gold solid.
- After cooling the molten mixture, the gold-antimony alloy is then ground into exceptionally fine talc and combined with *Butter of Antimony* (*Eagle's Glue* - liquid antimony menstruum) in the required proportions.

Stone of the Third Degree or Stone of the Third Order ⁽¹⁾ (also known as the *Chemical Wedding* to Islamic alchemists): this ultimate step completes Stone synthesis.

It is an amalgamation of gold-antimony glass or alloy mixed with Butter of Antimony subjected to seven cycles of intense heating in a crucible.

The antimony used passes through three stages:

- Purification
- Union
- Fixation

This yielded a fine reddish-brown colored powder that could be suspended in water and ingested.

Those alchemists who instead sought to “transmute” metals into a “nobler” state (from base metal like lead or copper to gold or silver) took the completed Stone and further treated it with mercury to create the *Philosophers' Child*. They used this new substance to “aurify” a metal, giving it a “gold-like” appearance. ⁽¹⁾

Ars Brevis (Brief Art) or the ***Via Sicca***, (Dry Path) – the metallurgical technique where “fermentation” of the Stone is achieved by heating the mixture in a crucible at an extremely elevated temperature, completing the synthesis in a shorter time.

The *Ars Brevis* is the most ancient method used to manufacture the Stone, known to the Semitic Akkadians from Mesopotamia or the Semitic populations that migrated to Egypt from the Mediterranean. ⁽¹⁾

Ars Magna (Great Art) or the ***Via Humida*** (Wet Path) – is the archetypal procedure used to make the Stone. Its origin is attributed to the previously mentioned Maria Hebraea of Alexandria (200 AD), an alchemist who specialized in preparing perfumes, herbal medicines, glass production and dyes for textiles.

Hebrea lived in a thriving Jewish quarter founded in Alexandria in 332 BC by Alexander the Great. ⁽¹⁾ By 200 AD, this district had become the largest Jewish community in the ancient world.

Maria Hebrea and her fellow Alexandrian alchemists were best renowned for *aurification*, also known as *chrysopoeia*, ⁽¹⁾ producing extremely high-quality bronze, almost indistinguishable from gold.

Of note, the renowned Alexandrian craftsmen from Hebrea's learned academy active between the 1st to 3rd centuries AD were among the earliest alchemists in recorded history. ⁽¹⁾

The secret fluxing agent used by Hebrea, and her colleagues was Sal Ammoniac (NH_4Cl). ⁽¹⁾

When Hebrea writes about the production of the Stone via the *Ars Magna*, she refers to the Four Stones:

- **The Black Stone (stibnite; Sb_2S_3) (First Stone)** – an inexpensive black powder sold in Alexandrian markets used as an eye cosmetic by both men and women.
- **The White Stone (Flowers of Antimony; $\text{Sb}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{Sb}_2\text{S}_3$) (Second Stone)** – obtained by heating mercury with stibnite in open air, first turning red, then yellow, and finally white.
- **The Red Stone (Latten; $\text{Au} \cdot \text{Sb}_2\text{O}_2\text{SO}_4$) (Third Stone)** – this substance is produced by repeatedly adding stibnite to molten gold, creating an alloy between the two, reducing the gold to a brittle, powdery brick-red metallic oxide.
- **The Violet Stone (Tincture; $\text{Au} \cdot \text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$) (Fourth Stone – Powder of Projection)** – made by taking the Red Stone and mixing with finely powdered fluxing salt (Sal Ammoniac), followed by heating to an elevated temperature to remove all oxygen and water.

When Hebrea used the *Ars Magna*, she mixed the first three “Stones” and placed the combination into a sealed, thick-walled glass flask. Hebrea believed the air-tight vessel was paramount to the process' success.

The mixture is heated for a prolonged period at a low furnace temperature until the three components liquefy and achieve fusion.

Subsequently, the container is subjected to increasing heat to remove any remaining water or oxygen, yielding the esteemed red gold-antimony crystals. ⁽¹⁾

Corinthian Bronze – This was a rare, exquisitely finished, antimonial-gold bronze prized throughout the Roman Empire.

Hebrea produced this alloy by taking the *Powder of Projection* (Fourth Stone) and fusing it with antimonial bronze. She would subsequently treat this special bronze with mineral acids. This etched its surface and rendered a deep purple patina to its facade.

The alchemists of Alexandria viewed the physical change of the bronze to a purple-tinged metal as a type of transmutation.

The Corinthian bronze thus obtained was a highly profitable commodity for Hebrea and her followers.

In addition, Alexandrian alchemists used the Powder of Projection mixed with rock-crystals to manufacture artificial rubies and diamonds. ⁽¹⁾

Synesius of Cyrene (373-412 AD), a prominent Neo-Platonist, mathematician, astronomer, and philosopher who lived in Alexandria after 393 AD, championed an alternate process used to produce the Philosophers' Stone. ⁽¹⁾

Synthesis of Synesius' White Stone of Hermes

1) Exaltation

2) Whitening

3) Reddening

Most successful Alexandrian, Islamic and European alchemists' efforts yielded a species of red-colored, colloidal gold-antimony oxysulfate crystals, the coveted prize:

Alembic Distillation Set

An ancient glassware design employed by alchemists consisting of a boiling flask on the bottom and an upper air-cooled head with an angular arm to collect the distillate. The condensed distillate is then dripped into another flask. (Original Artwork – S.E.S. Medina, MD)

Modern Medical Applications of the Philosophers' Stone

Aurum Potabile (“gold that is safe to drink”) was the medicinal form of the Philosophers' Stone deemed to bequeath perfect psychiatric and physical health. ⁽¹⁾

Alchemists alleged the innate perfection of the Stone in a powdered state or suspended in water brought the bodily fluids (humors) into balance. This “balance” would augment the individual's body's ability to resist disease, rejuvenate and foment a youthful appearance.

It was also claimed the Stone administered as an elixir could unlock deeper intelligence, mental faculties, and inner spiritual strength.

However, the name *aurum potabile* is misleading, as the elixir is a combination of gold *and* antimony. ⁽¹⁾

Kashyapa, a revered Vedic sage of Hinduism, stated the ingestion of gold augmented intellectual abilities, improved digestive and metabolic function, increased stamina, was an aphrodisiac, and prolonged life. ⁽¹²⁾

Hindus referenced *Hiranya* (synonymous with *Swarna Bhasma*), in the prehistoric Vedic works 1-2. ⁽⁹⁾⁽¹²⁾

Moses, the First Alchemist

“And he took the (golden) calf which they had made, and burnt it in the fire, and ground it to powder, and scattered it upon the water, and made the children of Israel drink of it.” Exodus 32:20.

In the biblical event depicted above (~1500 BC), Moses has just returned from the summit of Mt. Sinai with the Ten Commandments. He finds the Hebrews conducting an orgy around a calf idol cast from their collective gold jewelry.

Moses seizes the golden calf worshipped by the sinful Israelites and converts it into drinkable gold. This is the earliest record of processed gold consumed by human beings. ⁽¹⁾

In addition, Moses is the first human described in any written historical account credited with creating powdered gold and then administering it in a ritualistic manner to the Hebrews. It has earned Moses the dubious title of “The First Alchemist.” ⁽¹⁾

Converting the gold into an extremely fine powder (nano-particle colloidal suspension) followed by ingestion is the centerpiece of the psycho-spiritual medicine central to the metaphysical groundwork of the Philosophers' Stone.

Scholars debate whether Moses' possessed the required chemical knowledge to reduce gold to a powder centuries before the Alexandrian alchemists, in addition to using it as a medicinal to augment the spiritual and physical well-being of the Israelites.

The Bible describes Moses fleeing to the land of Midian after slaying an Egyptian who was torturing Hebrew slaves working on the pyramids (Exodus 2:11-15).

Moses spent forty years in self-exile, meeting Jethro, a high priest of Midian, and marrying one of his daughters (Zipporah).

Jethro was a Kenite, a people who had migrated from South Asia, bringing with them their knowledge of metallurgy. As High Priest, Jethro would have overseen the most important temple of the region, the Hathor Temple at Serabit el-Khâdim.

This temple possessed large-scale smelting and metallurgical facilities. According to the Bible, Hathor was only a few miles away from Mount Sinai, Mount Horeb, and the highest mountain in the region, Serabit el-Khâdim.

As a former member of the royal family, Moses would be familiar with Hathor, as the Egyptians had a robust trade with the metallurgists at the temple.

Archeologists have determined vast amounts of gold were transported in ancient times to Hathor for processing. These facts give credence to the possibility Moses possessed the technological knowhow, and the required starting materials to convert the golden calf to nano-particle gold. ⁽¹⁾

Per the alchemist Paracelsus, who championed the *Ars Brevis* method, Moses used a metallurgical rather than chemical process to produce the nano-particle gold: ⁽¹⁾

This technique is repeated twelve times, yielding a red powder (nano-particle gold), the Philosophers' Stone.

One last point of controversy: was Moses disciplining the Israelites by forcing them to drink the suspended processed gold from the calf idol, or rather dispensing a rare psycho-spiritual medication? The biblical account does not clarify this mystery but given the ancient use of such processed gold by South Asian peoples, we can imply Moses' beneficial intent.

Medicinal Uses of Nano-Particle Gold

Over the centuries, many therapeutic uses have been attributed to gold. The most common among them was as a "nervine," a substance that could cure "nervous conditions," i.e., neurologic, and psychiatric afflictions, such as depression and epilepsy.

In the sixteenth century, Paracelsus used gold preparations to treat epilepsy. ⁽¹⁶⁾⁽¹⁷⁾

In the seventeenth century, gold-based "cordials" were listed in pharmacopoeias and used to treat ailments punctuated by a decrease in the "vital spirits," such as melancholia, fevers, fainting and "falling sickness" (epilepsy). ⁽¹⁸⁾

In the nineteenth century, gold was utilized as a remedy for syphilis. The French physician, J.A. Chrestien, published a paper ⁽¹⁹⁾ titled "Researches and observations on the effects of preparations of gold in the treatment of many diseases and notably in syphilitic maladies."

He observed that gold possessed far milder adverse effects when compared to the standard treatments based on mercury, the most commonly employed therapeutic used against syphilis at that time.

Chrestien was among the first modern physicians to notice that occasionally, administration of gold increased intellectual faculties, vitality, and sexual functioning.⁽¹⁹⁾ The compound he utilized was gold trichloride (AuCl₃).

James Compton Burnett, a physician, homeopath, and author of twenty-seven books listed in the National Library of Medicine published in 1879 a lengthy treatise on gold as a medicinal therapeutic. Burnett reported: "Gold is an excitant. The patients feel an indestructible sense of well-being, they feel themselves lighten (as they express it) ... The intellectual faculties are more active. It has been known to produce frequent erotic salacity on to painful priapism."⁽¹⁷⁾

The dosage he recommended ranged from 1.95 to 5.85 mgs gold trichloride. Of note, this is similar to the daily administered dose of modern antiarthritic gold-based drugs (6 mgs/day for auranofin – Ridaura).⁽¹⁷⁾

At the end of the nineteenth century and into the first decades of the twentieth, medical texts listed gold as a nervine, including the first *Merck Manual*.⁽¹⁷⁾

Based on the US pharmacopoeia of 1890, Potter's *Materia Medica* states "... salts of gold promote appetite and digestion, stimulate the cerebral functions, produce marked mental exhilaration... aphrodisiac effects on both sexes... increase of the menstrual discharge. Amenorrhoea and impotence... may be cured by it."⁽²⁰⁾

In 1942, *Stedman's Practical Medical Dictionary* listed gold bromide as a sedative, an effective therapeutic for headaches, epilepsies, and as a treatment for alcoholism.⁽²¹⁾

The American physician, Leslie Keeley (1832-1900), used chlorides of sodium and gold, with a third, closely guarded, "secret" ingredient to treat alcoholism as well as opiate and cocaine addictions.

The *Chicago Tribune* published an editorial on February 13, 1894, describing Keeley's amazing therapeutic accomplishments. It cited a summary of over 1,000 patients where greater than 90% achieved a long-term cure of their addictions. Keeley is estimated to have treated 100,000 patients over his lengthy career.

Unfortunately, the identity of his "secret" ingredient died with him.⁽¹⁷⁾⁽²²⁾

In the nineteenth century, microscopists observed stains made from gold salts had an unusual affinity for brain tissue, heightening the visual discrimination between white and gray matter, and for the discernment of neuroglia, astrocytes, nerve fibers, sheaths, and cells.⁽¹⁷⁾⁽²³⁾

Currently, the most common uses of gold-containing medications are in the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis, as anticancer therapeutics and in anti-infectives, as well as a replacement for steroids in asthma, pemphigus and SLE.⁽²⁴⁾⁽²⁵⁾⁽²⁶⁾

Primary adverse side-effects include skin and gastrointestinal reactions, and rarely painful neuropathy, insomnia, peripheral motor neuropathy, acute SLE and encephalopathy with depression, delirium, and psychoses. ^{(27) (28) (29)}

With cessation of gold therapy, patients' symptoms disappear, albeit slowly. ⁽²⁹⁾

Additional studies of the potential benefits of nano-particle gold therapy include:

- Potential protective effect of gold nanoparticles (Au-NPs) in a mouse reperfusion/focal cerebral ischemia injury study. Administration of 20 nm Au-NPs up-regulated anti-apoptotic proteins and down-regulated pro-apoptotic molecules. ⁽³⁰⁾
- Inhibition of pro-Alzheimer's disease amyloid- β aggregates. ^{(31) (32) (33)}
- Anti-angiogenesis effects of Au-NPs through inhibition of Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor/Vascular Permeability Factor (VEGF/VPF) and basic Fibroblast Growth Factor (bFGF), two key cytokines modulating angiogenesis in malignancy and in proliferative vitreo-retinopathy. ^{(34) (35)}
- Delivery of custom-ligand-synthesized Au-NPs covered with covalently linked monoclonal antibodies, peptides, and other molecular ligands deadly to the target malignant cells. ^{(36) (37) (38) (39) (40)}

One study, published in 1998, found administration of Au-NPs resulted in a 20% increase in IQ scores lasting 1-2 months after stopping gold treatment. ⁽⁴¹⁾

In infectious diseases, Au-NPs have been found to cross the normally impervious blood-brain-barrier easily. ⁽⁴²⁾

Other studies have found a relationship between HSV-1 cerebral infections and neurodegenerative disorders. ^{(42) (43) (44) (45) (46) (47) (48)}

One researcher discovered Au-NPs blocked HSV-1 infection in neuronal cell cultures, potentially obstructing the development of neurodegenerative symptoms due to CNS HSV-1. ⁽⁴⁸⁾

Gold-based compounds, such as auranofin, used to treat psoriatic arthritis, elevate the CD4+ T-cell counts in HIV patients. ⁽⁴⁹⁾

For the "modern alchemist," newer methods to manufacture Au-NPs have been discovered since the seminal work by Michael Faraday, who 150 years ago first observed colloidal gold solutions possess properties distinct from bulk gold. ⁽⁵⁰⁾

The unique characteristics of Au-NPs provide researchers new platforms to fashion custom-made therapeutics. Among these attributes are: a high surface-to-volume ratio, size- and shape-dependent optical and electronic features, and surfaces that can be altered by the addition of ligands with chemical functional groups such as amines, phosphines, and thiols.

By using these functional groups to anchor ligands chemically, components such as proteins, oligonucleotides and antibodies can be added, broadening the therapeutic possibilities, particularly in HIV and brain-related diseases. ^{(51) (52) (53) (54) (55) (56) (57) (58)}

In closing, I humbly advocate an “open-minded” approach to delving into the potential beneficial possibilities of nano-particle gold in human medicine and metaphysics.

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